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Evolutionary convergence of sensory circuits in the pallium of amniotes

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Abstract

The amniote pallium contains sensory circuits structurally and functionally equivalent, yet their evolutionary relationship remains unresolved. Our study employs birthdating analysis, single-cell RNA and spatial transcriptomics, and mathematical modeling to compare the development and evolution of known pallial circuits across birds (chick), lizards (gecko) and mammals (mouse). We reveal that neurons within these circuits' stations are generated at varying developmental times and brain regions across species, and found an early developmental

divergence in the transcriptomic progression of glutamatergic neurons. Together, we show divergent developmental and evolutionary trajectories in the pallial cell types of sauropsids and mammals. Our research highlights significant differences in circuit construction rules among species and pallial regions. Interestingly, despite these developmental distinctions, the sensory circuits in birds and mammals appear functionally similar, which suggest the convergence of high-order sensory processing across amniote lineages.

One Sentence Summary

Amniote brains have evolved separately to converge into a non-homologous, but functionally equivalent sensory circuit.

Main Text

The neocortex is the biological substrate underlying the sophisticated and complex functions performed by mammalian species including humans. Neocortical neurons connect to each other following a stereotyped pattern (1, 2). This canonical circuit is comprised of three types of pallial glutamatergic neurons, each fulfilling a specific role in the circuitry (Fig. 1A). Electrophysiological evidence supports that these circuits account for major neocortical functions (3) and could be a major breakthrough of mammalian evolution. However, other vertebrate species that do not display a neocortex have been shown to present corresponding circuits. In both birds and reptiles, sensory information is also processed within circuits comprised of three glutamatergic neurons, contained within the pallium. The evolutionary origin of these amniote circuits is a matter of intense debate. These could be homologues to neocortical circuits -and so derived from the same ancestral circuit- or analogues, having convergently evolved separately (4-6).

The relevant circuits in the three vertebrate groups - mammals (1), birds (7, 8) and non-avian reptiles (9)- are functionally similar. Briefly, in all three groups there is a specific neuronal population which receives thalamic inputs. These neurons connect to an integrator neuron which, in turn, sends its input to a third pallial neuron. This last neuron of the circuit projects the information out of the cortex, to either the thalamus, the brainstem or other subcortical structures. Beyond similarities in their location, type of information processed and neurotransmitters, the neuronal populations of these circuits share the expression of a handful transcription factors -such as Tbr1, Rorb, Satb2 or Ctip2 (9-12)- and electrophysiological

properties (13). Due to these functional and structural similarities (14), it has been suggested and maintained that all these amniote circuits are homologous (15), implying that an equivalent ancestral circuit was already present in the brain of the last common ancestor of amniotes around 320mya. This view contrasts with evidence from developmental biology which propose a divergent scenario for the evolution of the pallium (16, 17) as these circuits appear in developmentally non-comparable brain regions.

Development and evolution are tightly linked: variations in one of them dictate trends in the other one (18, 19). Because evolutionary homology implies inheritance from a common ancestor, the developmental trajectory must be conserved for arguing the conservation of homologous neurons and circuits. Here, we argue that understanding the developmental trajectory of a neuron or a circuit may unravel their evolutionary history (20, 21). Conserved homologous cell populations are those who share an equivalent developmental program. Therefore, the long-standing debate over the homology of the sensory circuit can only be resolved by comparing the developmental trajectories of neurons in these amniote circuits. To investigate this evolutionary relationship and potential homology, we compared the developmental and transcriptional trajectories over the course of the construction of pallial sensory circuits in three amniote species.

Results

Developmental construction of avian high-order sensory circuits.

Conserved homologous cells share their developmental history. To test whether mammalian cortical circuits have homologous circuits in other amniote species we determined the developmental trajectory of pallial sensory circuits in sauropsids. The temporal neurogenic construction of the mammalian cortical circuit is well known. By means of EdU injections at three different time points during the neurogenic period of the chick pallium (E4 to E9) we revealed the temporal construction of the avian sensory circuits (**Figs. 1,2, S01-S10**). We researched on the two pallial structures that have been proposed as neocortical homologues, the dorsal ventricular ridge (DVR; **Figs. 1, S01-S04, 09, 10**) and the hyperpallium (HypPall; **Figs. 2, S05-S08**). We found that none of these structures develops in an equivalent temporal sequence as that known for the mammalian cortical circuit.

First, we focused on the avian DVR, which was primarily considered the homologous of the neocortex according to its internal circuitry. A similarity with mammalian corticogenesis

was that both the glutamatergic neurons and the GABAergic interneurons of each circuit relay were generated mostly synchronously (**Figs. S02-04**). However, DVR developed following different temporal neurogenic instructions to those present in the developing cortex. Two crucial differences were: First, the first-generated neurons act as thalamic recipient neurons within the entopallium (EPall) and the BSS (**Figs. 1E-J and S01**), whereas in mouse other cortical populations are generated earlier to thalamic recipient neurons of layer 4; and second, latest-generated neurons of the DVR do not contribute to sensory processing, as they remain in the most medial nidopallium (**Figs. 1E-J and S01**). In the case of mammals, all cortical neurons contribute to the circuitry, and the latest generated neurons act as integrators of the circuit in supragranular layers 2 and 3.

Beyond timing differences in the formation of the sensory neurons, we also found other dissimilarities between these two circuits. GABAergic interneurons, widely conserved amongst vertebrate pallia, distribute differently in these circuits. For instance, parvalbumin-expressing interneurons of the DVR are nearly exclusively located in the thalamic recipient areas (**Figs. 1 and S02-03**), whereas in mammals these neurons are widely distributed across all cortical layers. Somatostatin-expressing neurons, on the contrary, are dispersed through all regions of the avian circuit (**Figs. 1 and S04**), whereas are preferentially confined to deep cortical layers in mammals.

In addition, other developmental features in charge of building these circuits were different between mammalian cortex and avian DVR. While the neocortex derives from the dorsal pallial (DPall) germinative zone, the DVR derives from the ventral pallium (VPall; **Fig. 1**). This is a different, discrete region of the embryonic pallium that differs from DPall in the expression of key transcription factors, cell lineage and mature structures derived (in mammals, VPall mostly generates the pallial amygdala and the pyriform cortex)(22). These ancestral early developmental regions are so deeply conserved that only cell types within the same territory are considered homologous. Thus, neocortex and DVR derive from non-homologous progenitor populations.

The trisynaptic circuit in the DVR represents the building block of its internal circuitry but it oversimplifies the true connections, as it also occurs in neocortical circuits. Importantly, the ventral mesopallium plays a significant role as integrator in the circuitry, by receiving both EPall and dorsal nidopallium (dNPall) connections and due to its efferences towards the Arcopallium (APall)(14). We researched its main neurogenic waves to evaluate its similarities to integrator neurons of the neocortex (**Fig. S05**). The main neurogenic timepoint of the ventral

mesopallium was the intermediate stages, similarly to the other integrator neurons of the dNPall. However, this is different to the late neurogenic timepoint of mammalian integrator neurons. And also, the ventral mesopallium is generated in the lateral pallium, a different developmental territory to the rest of the DVR circuit. These are all substantial developmental differences to the neocortical canonical circuit.

The DVR circuits described above mainly represent the visual and somatosensorial circuits present in the VPall. There is another sensorial circuit in the same developmental territory, the auditory Field L at the posterior nidopallium (23). We also assessed the sequence of neurogenesis of this circuit and found that most of its neurons were generated at late neurogenic timepoints (**Fig. S06**). This implies that this auditory circuits generates differently to other DVR circuits, and also different to the mammalian neocortical one.

We next examined the program of development of the HypPall. The mammalian neocortex and the avian HypPall are both DPall derivatives, for which the two structures are considered field homologous (16,17). We researched the same birthdated brains as for the DVR, but focusing on the neurogenic program of the HypPall. We also found key differences in the temporal generation of HypPall neurons (**Figs. 2 and S07-10**). HypPall neurogenesis happened much quicker than neocortical neurogenesis. Most HypPall neurons were generated during intermediate- and late-neurogenic stages (E6 and E8 stages in chick), and only a minor fraction of them were early generated. Both E6 and E8-generated HypPall neurons settled in all three HypPall functional columns (**Figs. 2 and S07-10**). Thus, differently from the mammalian cortex, HypPall neurons are not cell fate-determined by their time of generation. We did not identify any cell fate preference correlated to the neurogenic time of HypPall neurons (**Figs. 2G-J and S07-10**). This is a clear-cut difference to the neocortex, which shows a wide correlation between the time when a neocortical neuron is generated and its final function within the circuit. Interestingly, glutamatergic and GABAergic neurons of each HypPall column were generated synchronously at the same embryonic stage (**Figs. S07-10**), a shared feature with the DVR and the mammalian cortex.

In addition, the distribution of interneuron types was also different to that of mammalian cortical layers. The majority of parvalbumin-expressing neurons settled in the HI/HD (**Fig. S09**), a suggested homologous area of the integrator layers 2 and 3, whereas PV-expressing interneurons widely distribute through all cortical layers in mammals.

These data show evidence that the two main high order-sensory circuits in birds, DVR and HypPall, develop following a different program to that known in mammals ((**Figs. 1J and 2G**). That is, these circuits were not homologous and evolved exploiting different developmental instructions.

Neurogenic time of gecko pallial sensory circuits

Because birds possess a highly specialized brain in the diapsid taxon (24), we further characterized the developmental construction of sensory circuits in a non-avian diapsid species such as the ground Madagascar gecko *Paroedura picta*. This species displays a pallium with fewer specializations, that better resembled the ancestral condition of the amniote group (25). The gecko pallium receives and processes thalamic sensory information in two main structures, the DVR and the dorsal cortex (DC). We identified these structures by markers such as Tbr1 or Satb2 (**Fig. 3A**; Satb2 antibody recognizes both Satb2- and Satb1- expressing neurons). We performed in situ hybridization to detect the expression of known markers for long-range output neurons (*Etv1* and *Sulf2*, **Fig. 3B,C**) thalamic recipient neurons (*Satb1*, **Fig. 3B,E**) (26, 27), and so describe the location of the neurons executing these two functions. We also analyzed PV immunohistochemistry patterns, commonly expressed at the Rotundus nucleus in sauropsids, which is the main visual thalamic input to the DVR (**Fig. 3B,D**). Altogether, we identified the location of main types of gecko pallial neurons (**Fig. 3F**) and focus our attention on the crucial populations for the evolutionary comparison: in DC, long-range output cells settle layer 2, in line with available literature. Precisely, it has been shown that turtle DC neurons with higher similarity to cortical long-range output neurons locate the upper half of layer 2 (11). In addition, *Satb1* expression is nearly absent in layer 2, suggesting thalamic recipient neurons locate layer 3 (**Fig. 3E**). As for the DVR circuitry, we identified that the thalamic recipient neurons were located at the outer region of the DVR, according to *Satb1* expression, and to neuropil staining of PV from rotundal axons.

We then performed equivalent birthdating experiments to those in chick, EdU injections at three different time points during the neurogenic period of the gecko pallium (E7 to E15) in order to reveal the temporal construction of the reptilian sensory circuits (**Fig. 3G,J**). The developmental program giving rise to the DVR, in the VPall, followed a clear outside-first inside-last gradient of neurogenesis (**Fig. 3I,J**). Early born (E7) DVR neurons of the gecko located the outer-most region of the DVR, deep beneath the lateral cortex. At intermediate stages (E11), newborn neurons tended to locate the central portions of the DVR. Finally, latest-

generated neurons (E15) hardly migrated away from the ventricular surroundings and located in the inner-most DVR region. An equivalent outside-in gradient of neurogenesis also led the formation of the DC, in the DPall, although not as sharp clear as in the DVR (**Fig. 3G,J**). Early-generated neurons (E7) in the dorsal cortex mostly locate the compact, cell-dense layer 2 (L2). At intermediate stages (E11), newborn neurons settle L3 and the deep stratum of L2, suggesting that the earliest neurons locate the upper half of layer 2. The latest generated neurons barely separate away from their original site at the ventricular zone, and locate the deepest stratum of L3.

This sequential neurogenesis verified that, akin to chicks but in stark contrast to the mouse neocortex, the initial neurons generated in the VPall sensory circuit in geckos were thalamic recipient neurons. The neurogenic progression observed in the DVR appears to be conserved in sauropsids, deviating from the pattern observed in mammals. Regarding the DPall sensory circuit, it is probable that geckos and mammals exhibit shared neurogenic characteristics. In both taxa, the long-range output neurons emerge as the first neurons in the circuit, diverging from the pattern observed in any avian pallial circuit. These data support the notion that pallial circuits develop differently across amniotes, revealing an unexpected evolutionary diversity.

Single RNA sequencing of early-born pallial populations

To confirm that the glutamatergic neurons of these amniote circuits are not conserved homologous cells, we proceeded to compare their transcriptional signatures and trajectories during development. We used our original *BirthSeq* method (28) to isolate and analyze birthdated cells days after their generation time. This method allowed us to compare those chick and mouse pallial neurons that were generated at equivalent neurogenic timepoints. By applying *BirthSeq*, we performed single cell RNA sequencing (scRNAseq) on cells generated early during the formation of the pallial circuits, both in chick (cells born at E4-E6 period, **Fig. 4A**) and in mouse (cells born at E12-E14; **Fig. 4D**). We focused on the earliest-born pallial neurons because these were shown to play divergent roles in the sensory circuit of the two species (**Figs. 1,2**).

BirthSeq provided us two datasets of maturing cells (11 days after EdU administration) enriched in neurons generated early in pallial development (**Figs. 4** and **S11-14+**, as also detailed in (28)). Chick pallium dataset comprised 3123 neurons distributed in 8 clusters (**Figs. 4A-C** and **S13-14**); Mouse pallium dataset comprised 3634 neurons distributed in 9 clusters

(**Fig. 4D-F and S11-12**). Each species' dataset comprised both glutamatergic neurons generated within the pallium and GABAergic interneurons that migrated tangentially from the subpallium (29–31). At a first glance, when comparing the differentially expressed genes (DEs) of these neurons, we observed that many of them were not common amongst the glutamatergic clusters of the two species, whereas there were more similarities in the GABAergic clusters (**Figs. 4C,F and S11-14 heatmaps**). For instance, mouse glutamatergic clusters (*Neurod6*, *Slc17a6*) were identified by the expression of *Sox11*, *Id2*, *Pcp4* and *Mef2c* genes (**Fig. S11**), whereas in the case of chick glutamatergic cluster the DE genes were *NRN1*, *NRP2*, *PPP1R17*, *TENM3* or *SATB2* (**Fig. S13**). In the case of GABAergic clusters (*Nrxn3*, *Gad*), some clusters shared the expression of interneuron subtypes such as *SST*, *ZFHX3*, *ADARB2* or *MEIS2* (**Figs. S12 and S14**). In order to compare cells from both species, we integrated the two datasets to visually understand cell similarities (**Fig. 4G**). GABAergic interneurons largely overlapped in the integrated UMAP and formed mixed clusters at different resolution values, pointing out to transcriptomic similarities. Glutamatergic neurons, on the other hand, tended to arrange in a more disperse, species-specific organization, with a clear example in Cajal-Retzius cells (msGLUT-05, *Reln*, *Lhx1*, the first cells to be generated in the cortical neuroepithelium (32, 33)), which were specific of the mouse dataset. The integrated dataset clustering showed that, amongst the 6 glutamatergic clusters, 4 were considered species-specific (2 chick-specific, 2 mouse-specific, with over 85% cells coming from the main species), whereas none of the 4 GABAergic clusters comprised such a majority of cells from one single species (**Fig. 4H**). The broader transcriptomic similarity of GABAergic neurons was then confirmed by the correlation of gene specificity indexes (Gene Specificity Index, GSI;(11)) (**Fig. 4I**). When comparing the transcription factors (TFs, genes more involved in cellular specification during development), expressed in the two datasets, the largest correlations (up to 0.86) were found among GABAergic cells. Remarkably, transcriptomic correlation was larger between pairs of clusters, suggesting transcriptomic equivalence in a one-to-one cell type fashion. However, only one chick glutamatergic cluster (ckGLUT-04) was found similar to two mouse clusters (msGLUT-03 and -04). No other cell type-to-cell type equivalence was identified. The general GSI similarities between glutamatergic neurons seemed more related to the transcriptional profile leading the glutamatergic phenotype than to the actual transcriptome involved in specific cell type differentiation. We tested this possibility by comparing the expression of each cluster DE genes, which tend to play roles in the specification of cell types (**Fig. 4L**). We generated modules comprising the most DE genes, from either the whole sequenced transcriptome or only from the transcription factor gene family, and analyzed the average expression of these

modules in the cell clusters of the opposite species. In the modules comprising the 5 most differentially expressed TFs for each cluster (**Fig. 4L**) GABAergic cells seemed to be more similar at cell-type level, regardless of the original species used for defining the module. In the case of glutamatergic cells, these shared a common background similarity, especially when mouse clusters were to define the module of expression. ckGLUT-04 cluster (*SATB2*, *MEF2C*, *CCK*, *CRHR2*, **Fig. S13**) was the most similar to a mouse cluster (msGLUT-04, *Mef2c*, *Ptprk*, *Arpp21*, **Fig. S11**) between the glutamatergic clusters. This mouse cluster corresponded to intratelencephalic cortical neurons (28), and its cells were likely the latest generated in our experiment. Then, we performed label transfer analysis (6) to interrogate each cell from a dataset what cell cluster from the other species dataset were transcriptionally more similar to. This test ultimately confirmed the larger cell type similarity between early born GABAergic neurons respect to early born glutamatergic neurons (**Fig. 4J**). Altogether, these analyses evidenced that early-born glutamatergic neurons showed divergent transcriptomes, as expected from their different developmental origin and circuit function. GABAergic cells, on the other hand, showed higher conservation at transcriptional level.

As a final comparison we asked whether chick early-born glutamatergic neurons expressed the typical molecular signatures of either upper-layer or deeper-layer neurons of the mouse cortex (27). We identified that some typical TFs and genes were expressed by one or more chick clusters, but the combination of those TFs typical of a cortical cell type was not found in any chick cluster (**Fig. 4K**). As a conclusion, early-born chick glutamatergic neurons are not only different to mouse early-born glutamatergic neurons at several levels of comparison, but these chick cells are also not similar to either upper- nor deeper-layer cortical neurons. Their transcriptional signature evolved separately from that of both mammalian types.

To understand how early-born glutamatergic neurons diverged in their maturing transcriptome we analyzed the transcriptomic developmental trajectories of these neurons. We birthdated early cells (E4 in chick, E12 in mouse) and applied BirthSeq two days only after EdU administration. We then sequenced birthdated cells comprising early differentiating neuroblasts and progenitors at intermediate pallial neurogenesis (E6 in chick and E14 in mouse) (**Figs. 5 and S15-18**). We performed an equivalent comparison of both species datasets as the one depicted above, including cell cluster identification, integration of datasets, GSI correlation, DE module analysis and label transfer. These experiments brought up three main results. First, that amongst the different cellular types sequenced, the largest similarities were found amongst the neural stem cells of both species. Specifically, pallial radial glial cells

(RGCs) were strongly similar at transcriptomic level (**Fig. 5**). Interestingly, we did identify a population of mouse intermediate precursor cells (IPCs) enriched in *Eomes* expression, but its identification in chick was elusive (19). No transcriptomically equivalent population of IPCs was found in the chick dataset as shown by the lack of merged IPC cells in the integration of the two datasets (**Fig. 5G**). But when the integration was performed without the usual cell cycle correction (**Fig. S17**) the ckGLUT-01e cluster showed a fraction of cells with some mouse IPC features. Also, there were abventricular division in a germinative SVZ of the developing chick pallium (**Fig. S17G**). Therefore, intermediate precursors of novel transcriptomic nature did exist in the chick pallium, but its relevance over pallial neurogenesis seemed restricted by their low numbers. Secondly, GABAergic cells showed the largest similarities between specific cell types also during their differentiation progress (**Fig. 5**). This implied that the transcriptomic divergence was determined from very early on in their development. And finally, we observed that some transcriptomic dissimilarities between glutamatergic cells were early determined from their neuronal birthdate. Glutamatergic cells from both species showed transcriptomic similarities related to the differentiation of main glutamatergic type (*TBR1*, *SLC17A6*, *NEUROD* genes), and a minor equivalence of specific cell types. As described above, these divergences were more pronounced between the maturing neuron datasets.

Our scRNA-seq analysis of early-born neurons of the pallium showed substantial disparities between the transcriptomic programs of GABAergic respect to glutamatergic neurons of both species. These programs were mainly divergent on the glutamatergic populations, whereas deeply conserved between GABAergic neurons.

Distribution of early-born chick pallial neurons

The location of specific cell types within the chick pallium remains largely unknown. To investigate and describe the distribution of these distinct cell types, we conducted *in situ* sequencing (ISS) for genes identifying early-born neuronal clusters (**Figs. 5, S19-S21**). Using 84 genes selected from the scRNAseq dataset we examined their expression at a cellular level in coronal sections of three E15 chick brains. Many of these genes were expressed exclusively in different telencephalic sectors, enabling the identification of various pallial territories and circuit stations (**Figs. 6A, S20**).

A total of 911495 cells were sequenced and analyzed. By comparing ISS reads to clusters identified through scRNAseq, we detected 660117 neurons in the tissue that likely corresponded to the scRNAseq clusters (**Fig. 6B**). This correspondence was determined by the

expression levels of significant genes in the ISS data (**Fig. 6B,C**). Glutamatergic neurons were found to be distributed in four clusters across different pallial regions, exhibiting distinct gene expression patterns and functions within the pallial circuitry (**Fig. 6D,E, S19**). GABAergic interneurons also displayed differential distribution among four neuronal clusters, with some spanning the entire pallium and others being more restricted to specific regions (**Fig. 6D,F**). The distribution identified through this probabilistic cell typing reflects our scRNAseq clusters correspond to major types of developmental neurons, but not all those neurons were early-generated.

To identify the early-born neurons among these clusters, we employed Neurogenes-iss, a combination of ISS and EdU birthdating (28). A fraction of 12.3% of the identified neurons within these clusters were EdU+, indicating their generation shortly after E4 EdU administration. The proportion varied across clusters (from 17.2%: ckGLUT-02 to 5%: ckGABA-04). Neurogenes-iss facilitated the precise localization of early-born neurons, along with their transcriptomic identity (**Fig. 6G,H and S19,S21**). The distribution of early-born neurons ckGLUT-01 to ckGLUT-03 aligned with expectations within the circuit (EPall, APall), as well as other pallial territories, such as the hippocampal and parahippocampal areas, nidopallium caudale, and mesopallium (**Fig. S20**). Remarkably, early-born neurons belonging to cluster ckGLUT-04, which exhibited similarity to msGLUT-04 (**Figs. 4, S18**), predominantly corresponded to mesopallial cells, and were therefore located outside the canonical circuit (4, 34). They were found in the mesopallium and hyperpallium, with some sparsely distributed in parahippocampal areas and APall.

Early-born GABAergic neurons exhibited a preference for subpallial territories but were also widely distributed throughout the pallial territories (**Fig. S21**). Notably, early-born GABAergic PVALB+ neurons in the EPall, primarily generated at E4 in chick (**Fig. 1 and S03**), were absent in our ISS analysis, possibly due to their absence in our initial scRNAseq. Overall, our novel analysis of early-born neurons' transcriptomics and distribution in the pallium confirmed their expected presence in various pallial regions. Glutamatergic neurons identified within the circuit regions corresponded to thalamic recipient neurons and long-range output neurons, while those outside the circuit belonged to integrator classes in other pallial territories, including the hippocampal and olfactory areas. These findings demonstrate that early-born neurons in the chick pallium differ from their counterparts in the mouse pallium at developmental, transcriptomic and distribution levels. These divergent neurons are generated from homologous radial glial cells, which follow divergent developmental programs to

generate different neurons in mouse and chick. And ultimately, neurons assemble into non-equivalent stations of the pallial circuitry.

Functional constraints limit circuit architecture

While developed differently, mouse and chick pallial circuits supersede sensory processing alike (35). We resort to mathematical modeling to elucidate the possible principles for such functional convergence. Each pallial circuit consists of a population of neurons functionally connected prominently by volume transmission and electrical coupling (36). Thus, there is no preferential connection between one cell and another: cell connections within individual pallial circuits and across are normally distributed around zero (no coupling) by their electrical field fluctuations propagating by the extracellular milieu. Thus, the whole pallial circuit can be modeled by a block random matrix \mathbf{J} , where connections within pallial areas will generally have different standard deviations (g_r) from those across regions (g_x) due to their different physical (spatial) constraints (Supplementary notes). The theory of random matrices then tells us that the activity of pallial circuits is dominated by the leading eigenvalue Λ_1 of the matrix reflecting the block structure of such deviations (37).

We “grow” pallial circuits by progressively increasing the size of our matrix blocks, adding neurons at fixed time stamps based on the neurogenesis probability inferred from our data (**Fig. 7A,B**). The functional readout of this process is the change in the eigenvalue spectrum of the pallial connectivity matrix \mathbf{J} (**Fig. 7C,D**), which is contained in a circle of radius Λ_1 . Then, the appearance of spontaneous ongoing activity emerging in late embryonic stages and persisting after birth is reflected in our model by Λ_1 values growing to one and beyond. This can be achieved by constraining the strength of neuronal connections within vs. between regions (38). In particular, neither of the connection types alone can account for such emergence, but it is necessary for both connections to be sufficiently strong for the circular spectrum to grow beyond the unitary circle (**Fig. 7E**). Intriguingly, despite the divergent neurogenic programs and structural differences, similar values of coupling strength can be found in both mice and chicks, resulting in similar circuit activity as reflected by similar Λ_1 curves above one towards approaching birth. This, in turn, suggests that neurogenesis programs in the avian vs. mammalian brain may have converged by evolutionary constraints for adaptation to equivalent functions.

To test the latter hypothesis, we look at the propensity of the circuit to be active in the function of neurogenesis, estimating the spectral energy of the graph associated with the

matrix \mathbf{J} , that is, the sum of all eigenvalues (in absolute value) of \mathbf{J} (39). As we permute the three neurogenic programs across the pallial/cortical regions, we prove that avian and mammalian circuits have evolved to maximize energy independently with respect to neuronal coupling strength (Fig. 7F). Given that activity promotes neuro and synaptogenesis, and vice versa (40), maximizing the energy function supports the notion that the evolutionary divergence of avian and mammalian circuits is necessary to optimize their genesis. Both avian and mammalian circuits evolved by functional channeling into equivalent circuits. These circuits converged to respond to the same functional requirements

Discussion

For decades, there has been a heated debate revolving around identifying homologies between the mammalian-specific neocortex and that of other vertebrates. Various claims have emerged regarding these homologies, based either on gene expression patterns observed in embryonic brains or on neuronal connectivity patterns found in adult brains. Here we tackled the debate from alternative views, researching the developmental formation of the pallial circuitry from neurogenic, transcriptional and mathematical perspectives. We uncover that the developmental rules for the construction of these circuits are different in each species and for each pallial region (Fig. S22). The neurons of the three stations of the circuit are generated in different developmental times and brain regions. Amniote species also differ in the progenitors required to generate the circuit, as evidenced by the difference in the pallial sources, and the nature and relevance of IPCs. Moreover, by means of single cell RNA sequencing we reveal that equivalent pallial neurons (those generated in homologous brain regions and equivalent neurogenic times) mature into divergent neuronal types, confirming that the formation of the circuits follows different developmental and evolutionary paths in sauropsids and mammals. Finally, mathematical modelling shows evidence that the sensory circuits of birds and mammals are sculpted by the same functional constraints. Altogether, we demonstrate that the circuits in charge of high-order sensory processing have evolved separately in different vertebrate taxa to converge into a functionally similar circuit.

In our comparison, we operate under the assumption that traits which are conserved must also exhibit equivalence in their developmental programs. Homology, in this context, implies the sharing of a feature that originated from a common ancestor (as discussed in (19)). Our assumption is grounded in the belief that the last common ancestor of amniotes already possessed a pallium (41). If the circuits of present-day species were indeed conserved and

homologous, then they should have inherited the same developmental program that was already present in the pallium of the last common ancestor. This assumption has proven to be valid when applied to other distinct brain territories. Recently, through the utilization of the same birthdating techniques across multiple amniote species, we have discovered that the developmental sequence responsible for generating cerebellar circuitry is profoundly conserved (42). Purkinje cells, GABAergic interneurons and granule cells of the cerebellar cortex, all are generated following the same temporal sequence in mouse, chick and gecko. In addition, cerebellar neurons are deeply conserved at transcriptomic level (43, 44). These similarities prove that the evolutionary conservation of a brain structure is reflected, and promoted, by its developmental conservation. It is this developmental conservation which causes evolutionary conservation. The fact that the pallium develops its circuitry in several different ways strongly supports a non-homologous character of the amniote pallial circuits.

Another crucial factor indicating the divergent nature of these circuits in amniotes is the significant differences in their progenitor cells. These differences occur at anatomical level, but also at progenitor cell type level. In mammals, the neocortex is generated in the dorsal pallium from multipotent radial glial cells (45–47). However, in birds, the proposed homologous circuit develops in the ventral pallium, which is a distinct pallial territory that predominantly gives rise to the amygdala and olfactory structures in mammals (30, 48). Progenitors in the ventral pallium exhibit transcriptomic differences from those in the dorsal pallium, reside in distant regions of the pallium, and are not evolutionary equivalents (16).

Furthermore, neural stem cells in charge of generating the neurons of the circuits differ at their neurogenic potential. In birds, no single progenitor can generate all the neurons of the DVR circuit. Through electroporations that reveal whole-cell lineage and neuronal migration in chicks, it has been demonstrated that progenitors in the VPall can generate neurons for either the EPall and dNPall, or the APall (30, 49). Therefore, at least two differentially located progenitors are necessary to assemble a functional circuit. This is a crucial difference to mammals, on which a single radial glial cell is capable of generating each and all the different types of neurons of the cortical circuit (45–47). But also, it is important to note that at intermediate stages of pallial neurogenesis in chicks (around E6), only a small proportion of pallial division happens in the SVZ, and its constituent progenitors are not transcriptomically similar to mouse IPCs despite *EOMES* expression. At the equivalent neurogenic timepoint in mouse cortical neurogenesis (E14 in mouse) intermediate progenitor cells (IPCs) reach their peak population (50, 51). These facts point to differences in the direct and indirect neurogenic

pathways, a feature previously referred as an evolutionary difference between sauropsids and mammals (52). Hence, the cellular trajectory of early born pallial neurons in birds differs from that of mammals at all the examined levels, which led to transcriptomic differences in these early-born populations. It is likely, though, that IPCs play a more relevant role in avian pallial neurogenesis later in development, as shown in a parallel article after a complete description of the developing cell types in the chick pallium (53).

Altogether, our data show an early transcriptomic divergence in the glutamatergic cell types, which differ between chick and mouse as early as two days after their generation. This divergence of glutamatergic profiles has been further confirmed by two independent articles, which employ different methodologies in developing, post-hatching and adult chicks. Zaremba et al. (53) performed a thorough atlas of the transcriptomic profiles of the pallium of chick, and Hecker and Kempynck et al. (54) used a novel deep learning analysis to characterize cell-type specific enhancer codes. In both cases, when compared amongst amniote species, glutamatergic cells were the most divergent cell types in the pallium. And amongst those neurons displaying similarities are mesopallial cells, a shared result in all three studies.

On the contrary to glutamatergic cells, our data, as well as those described in parallel articles (53, 54), point to a strong conservation of GABAergic pallial neurons. The developmental formation of interneurons follows equivalent sequences of neurogenesis. And transcriptomic analyses also show similar molecular fingerprints of these GABAergic populations. The conservation of GABAergic neurons of the pallium has been now shown equal for many different taxa. This conservation was, as stated before, demonstrated by similarities in developmental lineage and transcriptomic profiling. The vertebrate groups tested by transcriptomic comparison have been turtles (11), lizards (55), amphibians (56, 57), and the distant group of cyclostomes -lampreys- which are jawless vertebrates (58). The results on all these species were the same: homologous populations of GABAergic interneurons are generated in the subpallium, migrate tangentially into the pallium, differentiate into interneuron subtypes of equivalent transcriptomic profile and contribute to the function of pallial circuits. The molecular reasons behind this dual evolution of pallial circuits (diversified glutamatergic cells vs. conserved GABAergic cells) remain unknown.

The functional similarities between these circuits are explained by parallel convergent evolution, which guided the formation of the circuits under efficiency restrictions. Many species evolve in the same environment, under the same physical rules, and are driven by the same optimization constraints. This implies that functionality limits diversity, at all biological

levels. For circuit evolution as well, because circuits may act in similar ways in different species: the shared function of independent circuits limits the diversity of them. We speculate that, following this argument, pallial circuits are more efficient and optimal when arranged in this known fashion (14). Surely, evolution tinkered with their development, structure and function. But the surviving circuits, those selected after millions of years of evolution, display limited diversity because evolved under the same optimization criteria (35). Convergent evolution sculpted the formation of sensory circuits in amniote species.

Materials and methods summary

Animal use

All animal experiments were approved by a local ethical review committee and conducted in accordance with personal and project licenses in compliance with the current normative standards of the European Union (Directive 2010/63/EU) and the Spanish Government (Royal Decrees 1201/2005 and 53/2013, Law 32/107). All mice and gecko embryos were from our breeding colonies at Achucarro Basque Center for Neuroscience and the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU). Fertilized chick eggs were purchased from Granja Santa Isabel (Spain)

Birthdating

Pregnant mice and sauropsid embryos were injected with EdU at the experimental time according to specific protocols for each species (42). Upon completed neurogenesis, neuron migration and cell differentiation, animals were later sacrificed at the research time following standard anesthesia protocols. The brains were dissected and processed for subsequent experimentation.

Immunohistochemistry and EdU labeling

Brains were fixed with were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA, diluted in phosphate buffered saline 0.1M– PBS, pH 7.3) and sectioned in a vibratome microtome at 50–70 μ m thickness section. Single and double immunohistochemical reactions were performed as described previously (59) using a series of commercial primary and secondary antibodies. EdU molecule was later revealed following the *Click* reaction, with the commercial EdU Click-It kit (ThermoFisher).

BirthSeq

Isolation of birthdated cells for scRNAseq was performed as previously described (28). Briefly, chick and mouse embryos were birthdated at early neurogenic timepoints (E4 or E12, respectively) and sacrificed either two or eleven days after EdU injection. Birthdated cells were

FAC-Sorted from E14 mouse embryos, P3 mouse postnatal pups, E6 and E15 chick embryos, and were prepared for single cell capture of cells on 10X Genomics platform.

Data integration and clustering

The sequenced FASTQs were aligned and demultiplexed with 10X *Cell Ranger* v6.0.2. Afterwards, data matrices were imported to *R* (v4.1.0), where *Seurat* (v4.1.0) (60) was employed to further analysis. Cell cycle and mitochondrial percentage were both corrected through the *ScaleData()* function for cluster identification and *SCTransform()* for cross-species comparisons. The initial atlases were generated with subtle modifications of *Seurat* default parameters and functions at several low and high resolutions. To identify cell types, differential gene markers and scientific literature (*in situ* hybridization databases, our own experiments and single cell equivalent experiments from the literature (27, 61–63)) were used. This process was followed again after non-neural cells were subset to obtain the final neural atlases. These atlases were used for cross-species comparisons filtered by 1-to-1 orthologues (based on *biomaRt* tables, *Ensembl*) with the four complementary statistical analysis methods: Multi-Species Integration, Cluster-specific DE module expression analysis, *Gene Specificity Index (GSI)* Correlation (11) and *Label Transfer* (64) (see supplementary methods for details).

In situ hybridization (ISH)

Gecko embryonic brains were fixed in PFA for 10-20h and subsequently cut in a vibrating microtome at 50 μ m section thickness. M13forward (5'GCCAGGGTTTTCCAGTCAC3') and M13reverse (5'GGAAACAGCTATGACCATG3') primers were used to obtain the fragments from our cloned genes that were used to get riboprobes. Sense and antisense digoxigenin-11-UTP-labeled (Roche) riboprobes were synthesized according to the detailed procedures previously described (65).

In situ sequencing (ISS)

Brains were processed according to the direct RNA ISS method published in (66). Imaging was performed by a cyclic combinatorial labeling strategy as described in (67). After the last round of combinatorial imaging, the probes were stripped and EdU was labeled using a cross reactive BrdU antibody. The acquired images processed, denoised and decoded using the scripts from (66), deposited at https://github.com/Moldia/Lee_2023. The decoded gene expression data was assigned to individual cells based on close proximity to the nearest DAPI signal, using *StarDist* as a segmentation method (68). Cell-by-gene expression data was filtered removing cells with low read counts or suspected doublets, and then was integrated with the

scRNAseq datasets using probabilistic cell typing (69). The DAPI-based segmentation mask generated by StarDist was applied to the EdU images and the staining intensity was extracted for each nucleus, as described in (28).

Mathematical models

Random network models for mouse ($N=1000$) and chick ($2N$) were created, representing pallial circuits at birth (E18/P1 for mouse, E10/P1 for chick). Intra-region connections were $N(0, g_r)$ distributed, inter-region were $N(0, g_x)$. Mouse: $g_r=0.75$, $g_x=1.5$; Chick: $g_r=0.75$, $g_x=1.5$ or $g_r=0.5$, $g_x=2.0$. Neurogenesis was modelled backward in time by random neuron removal with region-specific probabilities obtained by metalog data fitting (see **Supplementary Notes S1** for details). Analysis of the leading eigenvalue followed (37).

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Author contributions: ERA and FGM conceived the project, interpreted the data, designed and performed experiments and data analysis, and wrote the manuscript with input from all authors. MTGF and AF performed embryo work and experiments. AMA, AB and AQG performed single cell RNA sequencing. EV and RSG performed bioinformatic analysis. LE, MR and MdMV performed FACS sorting analysis. MG, SMS and ERA performed and analyzed the *in situ sequencing* experiments. JLF, DG and AT performed and analyzed in situ hybridization. MP and FGM performed theoretical modeling. MN, AD, JME and FGM provided reagents.

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Data and materials availability: I

Data generated for this study have been submitted to the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO; <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>) under accession number GSEXXXXXX. The code used for analysis (scRNAseq processing, interspecies comparisons, spatial transcriptomics) can be found in <https://github.com/phylobrain/Rueda-Alana2024>.

Supplementary Materials

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Figures

Fig. 1. Neuronal birthdating of the chick DVR sensory circuit. (A) Schematic highlighting the connections of the mammalian cortical canonical circuit. Th: thalamus. (B) Equivalent schematic depicting the connections of the chick DVR canonical circuit. (C) Scheme of the basic cell type organization in the trisynaptic circuit of amniotes. MPall: mesopallium; SPall: subpallium; ThR: thalamic recipient area. (D) Example of coronal section of the chick telencephalon in a typical experiment, where EdU is labeled (white) along with two markers

by immunohistochemistry, PV (green) and Tbr1 (red). **(E)** Summary of the birthdating performed at early (E4, magenta), intermediate (E6, gold) or late (E8, cyan) neurogenic timepoints. Two coronal sections are shown, one anterior (top row) and one at posterior levels (bottom row). HT: hypothalamus; PTh: prethalamus. **(F)** Pseudoimage made by the merge of images coming from three different animals, showing the distribution of pallial cells according to birth time. **(G-I)** Quantitative analysis of the neurogenesis of DVR circuit cells. **(G)** Graphic representation of the temporal neurogenic construction of the different DVR circuit roles. The graph illustrates the normalized percentage of cells of each circuit role generated at early, intermediate or late neurogenic timepoints. **(H)** Graphic representation of the distribution of DVR circuit neurons generated at each analyzed neurogenic timepoint. **(I)** Graphic representation of the effect of age in the generation of the cells of each DVR circuit roles. Statistical tests for **(I, J)** are described in **Supplementary Materials**. **(J)** Summary of the comparative birthdating of mammalian cortical vs. avian DVR sensory circuits. The graph depicts the percentage of cells of each circuit role generated at early, intermediate or late neurogenic timepoints. Scale bars, 1 mm.

Fig. 2. Neuronal birthdating of the chick hyperpallial sensory circuit. (A) Schematic highlighting the connections of the mammalian cortical canonical circuit. (B) Equivalent schematic depicting the connections of the chick hyperpallial canonical circuit. HA: hyperpallium apicale; HI/HD: intermediate and densocellular hyperpallium; IHA: intercalated hyperpallial area. (C) Scheme of the basic cell type organization in the trisynaptic circuit of amniotes. (D) Example of coronal section of the chick telencephalon in a typical experiment, where EdU is labeled (white) along with two markers by immunohistochemistry, PV (green) and Tbr1 (red). (E) Summary of the birthdating performed at early (E4, magenta), intermediate (E6, gold) or late (E8, cyan) neurogenic timepoints. (F) At the right, pseudoimage made by the merge of images coming from three different animals, showing the distribution of pallial cells according to birth time. (G) Summary of the comparative birthdating of mammalian cortical vs. avian hyperpallial sensory circuits. The graph depicts the percentage of cells of each circuit station generated at early, intermediate or late neurogenic timepoints. (H-J) Quantitative analysis of the hyperpallial circuit neurogenesis. (H) Graphic representations of the temporal

neurogenic construction of the neurons of the different hyperpallial circuit roles. The graph illustrates the normalized percentage of cells of each circuit role generated at early, intermediate or late neurogenic timepoints. **(I)** Graphic representation of the distribution of hyperpallial circuit neurons generated at each analyzed neurogenic timepoint. **(J)** Graphic representation of the effect of age in the generation of the cells of each hyperpallial circuit roles. Statistical tests for **(I, J)** are described in **Supplementary Materials**. Scale bars, 250 μm .

Fig. 3. Neuronal birthdating of the gecko pallial sensory circuit. (A) Examples of immunostaining for general pallial markers (Tbr1 in green; SatB2 and SatB1 in red) in gecko coronal sections. DMC: dorsomedial cortex; MC: medial cortex; Str: striatum; aDVR: anterior DVR; Sph: spherical nucleus. (B) Scheme of two coronal sections of the gecko brain depicting the two main communications of the thalamo-pallial pathway: the lemnothalamic pathway reaching DC (turquoise green) and the collopallial pathway reaching the aDVR (magenta). Abbreviations in **Supplementary Materials**. (C) In situ hybridization (ISH) against *etv1* and *sulf2* mRNAs in the E35 gecko brain, markers of long-range output neurons in mice. Sagittal and coronal sections. Colorimetric staining, pseudotransformed in fluorescent gold staining on the right images. VZ: ventricular zone. (D) PV immunostaining in red, two coronal sections at the level of the thalamus (left) and of the telencephalon (right). PV stains rotundal neurons at the thalamus, part of the collothalamal pathway, and their projections reaching the lateral portion of the DVR. (E) Colorimetric ISH against *satb1*, marker of thalamic recipient neurons

in mouse cortex, in coronal sections of the E35 gecko telencephalon, pseudotransformed in fluorescent gold at the right image. *Satb1* expression is highest at the outer portion of the DVR in the collothamic pathway, and in the deeper layers of DC (L3 and deep L2). **(F)** Scheme depicting a coronal section of the chick telencephalon with the location of neurons of pallial circuits **(G,H)** Birthdating of the DC neurons at three neurogenic stages. **(G)** Images of the EdU labeling. At the right, pseudoimage made by the merge of images coming from three different animals, showing the distribution of DC cells according to birth time. **(H)** Quantification analysis of the birthdating in DC. **(I,J)** Birthdating of the DVR neurons at three neurogenic stages. **(I)** Images of the EdU labeling. At the right, pseudoimage made by the merge of images coming from three different animals, showing the distribution of DVR cells according to birth time. **(J)** Quantification analysis of the birthdating in DC. DAPI counterstain in blue in A, C, D, E, G and I. Colored scale bars: black, 1 mm; grey, 250 μm ; white 100 μm ; light purple, 50 μm .

Figure 4 – Transcriptomic comparison of chick and mouse early-born pallial neurons.

(A,F) Scheme depicting the extraction and analysis of early born neurons in the maturing pallium of chick (A) and mouse (D). (B,E) UMAP graph of the main types of chick (B) or mouse (E) early-born pallial neurons. (C,F) Gene expression UMAP graphs of two key markers for glutamatergic (*NEUROD6*) or GABAergic (*NRXN3*) neurons in chick (C) or mouse (F). (G) UMAP graph of the seurat integration merging the two species datasets. (H) Integrated UMAP clustering. At the right, proportion of each species cells to the integrated clusters. Bottom left, average proportion of neurons from each species in either glutamatergic or GABAergic clusters. Bottom right, proportion of clusters considered as species-specific or shared by both species. (I) Correlogram of gene specificity indexes between pairs of clusters of the two species. (J) Label transfer analysis of mouse cells onto the chick annotated reference UMAP. Right, proportion of cells from a mouse cluster that were assigned to a given chick cluster. (K) Gene expression DotPlots of key markers for glutamatergic cortical neurons (27) for each chicken glutamatergic cell type (L) Percentage of module expression for each cell type (Top4 Marker Genes) on the other species cell types (left, mouse modules; right, chicken modules).

Figure 5– Transcriptomic comparison of early-born neurons and progenitors between chick and mouse. (A-F) BirthSeq isolation of early born populations two days after Edu labelling in chick (A-C) and mouse (D-F). (A,D) EdU staining of chick and mouse pallia at the moment of cell isolation. (B,E) UMAP graph of the main types of chick (B) or mouse (E) early-born pallial populations. (C,F) Gene expression UMAP graphs of several key markers for RGCs (*NOTCH1*), IPCs (*INSM1*), glutamatergic neurons (*NEUROD6*), Cajal-Retzius cells (*LHX1*) or GABAergic (*DLX5*) neurons in chick (C) or mouse (F). (G) UMAP graph of the seurat integration merging the two species datasets. (H) Correlogram of gene specificity indexes between pairs of main cell types of the two species. (I) Correlograms of gene

specificity indexes between pairs of clusters of the two species, considering transcription factors only in the comparison. **(J)** Percentage of module expression for each cell type (Top5 Marker Genes) on the other species cell types. **(K)** Label transfer analysis of chick cells onto the mouse annotated referenc; proportion of cells from a chick cluster that were assigned to a given mouse cluster. DAPI counterstain in blue in A, D. Scale bars, 100 μm .

Figure 6 – Identification of early-born neurons of the chick pallium by *in situ* sequencing.

(A) Expression maps of 4 informative markers, chosen from a panel of 84 ISS genes. (B) Examples of in-situ probabilistic cell type assignment for the neuronal clusters: for each cell (identified using DAPI signal), a map of its associated transcripts is built, taking into account the probability of gene co-expression derived from scRNAseq data (images). Based on its expression profile, each cell is then assigned a probability of belonging to each one of the scRNAseq clusters (pie charts). (C) Heatmap comparison of the gene expression profiles, as detected by informative genes in ISS, of the different cell clusters. (D) Anatomical distribution of the glutamatergic and GABAergic neuronal sub-populations. Left panel shows the distribution of glutamatergic neuron types. (E-H) Joint birthdating and transcriptional profiling of selected cell clusters: Glutamatergic (E) and GABAergic (F) neuronal subclasses

distributions are shown on two of the samples, together with a description of their characteristic markers, anatomical distributions and functional annotations (table). Of each neuron subclass, the EdU-positive cells can be extracted and plotted separately (**G-H**), allowing to analyze the distribution, across neuron types, of the birthdated cells. This allows to visually inspect the relationship between birth date and cell identity. Scale bars in A and D, 500 μm . Sections were obtained from 3 different embryos.

Figure 7 – Mathematical modelling supports convergence by functional constraints.

(A,B) Mouse and chick pallial circuits and associated neurogenesis probabilities (PDF) reconstructed from available data (see **Supplementary Notes S1**). (C,D) Simulation of neurogenesis by growth of random networks with structured connectivity (top graphs, only 60% connections shown). (E) Emergence of spontaneous activity leads to network eigenvalues exceeding one for an appropriate choice of intra- vs. inter-region connection strength. (F) Spectral graph energy is maximal in the mouse and chick for the documented neurogenic program, but not for any other random permutation of the temporal sequence of the different neurogenic niches.